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Analyzing the What and How of United States Foreign Aid to Israel 2017-2020

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Abstract

The United States and Israel are two of the countries with the most unique relationship. The relationship between the two countries can be traced back to the very beginning of Israel's statehood. For most of modern history, a lot of conflicts involving Israel have erupted in the Middle East, some of which have endangered Israel's very existence. The unique relationship between the two countries has led the United States to view Israel as its main ally in the Middle East. Therefore, it is important for the United States to help Israel ensure its survival in this conflict-ridden region. One U.S. effort involves its foreign aid to Israel. Through this study, the authors attempt to explain the form and process of U.S. foreign aid to Israel in 2017-2020. This paper uses a qualitative method, with the data collected using document and internet-based methods. The primary data that are being used here are documents and reports on US foreign aid to Israel from 2017 to 2020 published directly by the US government. The findings show that the United States provided Israel with substantial military and non-military foreign aid in the period 2017-2020, and that the process of providing this aid is also progressing well.

Keywords: United States, US Foreign Aid, Military Aid, Non-Military Aid, Israel

1. Introduction

Israel and the United States have consistently had a close military relationship that reflects* shared security interests in the Middle East. A major purchaser and user of US military equipment, Israel is also involved in the joint development of military technology and is regularly involved in joint military exercises involving the United States and other countries. In addition, the United States also possesses a number of Israeli-owned military equipment that they not only use for training and testing purposes, but also for direct use by the United States armed forces.

The United States and Israel maintain a strong bilateral relationship for several reasons including strong domestic support for Israel and its security, common strategic goals in the Middle East, a shared commitment to democratic values, and historical ties since the creation of the Israeli state. United States foreign aid has been a major component in strengthening and reinforcing this relationship. Many United States politicians and lawmakers came to view Israel as an important ally in the Middle East, and the amount of aid the United States provided to Israel

has reflected that view. In the years following the 1973 Yom Kippur War, supporters of Israel launched a large and organized effort in the United States, to encourage bipartisan support for bilateral relations in the United States Congress, including United States aid to Israel. This effort is also known as the Israel Lobby (Sharp, U.S. Foreign Aid to Israel, 2022).

Israel has established close bilateral cooperation with the United States in various fields. The relationship between the United States and Israel is a mutually beneficial cooperation that strengthens the moral values and strategic interests of the United States, and promotes peace and stability. The United States' relationship with the Middle East's only democracy is one of the key pillars of the United States' regional security framework. Unlike other U.S. allies, Israel insists on defending itself, relying on U.S. assistance to provide Israel with the means and infrastructure to do so while advancing U.S. national security interests. This type of strategy is similar to what India has done with its foreign policy strategy in Indo-Pacific region. The Strategy, which is called buck-passing, aims to make some countries as proxies for its national interests (Juned, India's Foreign Policy in Indo-Pacific Region and Its Impact for Southeast Asia's Regional Interest, 2019). The strong bilateral relationship between the United States and Israel and increased bilateral cooperation in homeland security, cybersecurity, space, sustainability, and other areas help both countries and others around the world to meet the common challenges that arise in the contemporary era (Zanotti, 2022).

For most of modern history, the Middle East has been rife with conflict. Since the early nineteenth century, European powers have competed to colonize the region in an attempt to gain control of its natural resources and geostrategic location. Nearly two centuries later, the Middle East found itself a battlefield where superpowers and regional powers compete for territorial influence. The Middle East again became an arena of conflict after the Arab Spring phenomenon in the 2010s. Protests and uprisings that started as peaceful demands for democracy and freedom turned into civil and regional wars in many countries. The conflicts between Saudi Arabia and Iran in Lebanon, the West Bank and Gaza Strip, Iraq, Yemen and Bahrain have shaped the geopolitics of the region since the 2003 US invasion and occupation of Iraq. The presence of the Arab Spring phenomenon has intensified and made Syria also involved in this geopolitical contest (Salloukh, 2013).

2017-2020 was a unique period for bilateral relations between the United States and Israel. During this period, the United States was led by President Trump, who several times openly showed his pro-Israel stance. These include the United States' recognition of Jerusalem as the capital of Israel and the United States' recognition of Israel's sovereignty over the Golan Heights. In addition, Trump also supported many of the policies of Benjamin Netanyahu, who was the Prime Minister of Israel at the time. The United States' support for Israel is manifested in three different forms: political support, financial aid, and military aid. The United States and Israel have one of the strongest political and military alliances in the world. The United States' political support for Israel is not only about Palestine but also regional geopolitics (Erdoğan & Habash, 2020). The main factors at the core of the relationship are that the United States and Israel share common values, interests and goals in the Middle East.

Next, the author will present several literature reviews consisting of previous studies regarding foreign aid in general and objectives behind the US foreign aid to Israel. Robinson & Tarp (2000) stated in their study that throughout history, there had been several justifications for why a country gives foreign aid, namely altruism, political ideology, foreign policy, commercial interests, and economic development. Another study on the reasons behind foreign aid from Lancaster (2007) also more or less concur with what Robinson & Tarp (2000) had said. According to Apodaca (2017), when it comes to international politics, foreign aid is used primarily to promote geostrategic interests, to maintain friendly relations with foreign governments, to strengthen alliances, or to keep allied regimes in power. The following studies from Ali (2013) and Blankenship & Joyce (2019) share the same opinion regarding the objectives of US foreign aid to Israel. Both studies state that the US foreign aid to Israel is primarily driven by political and geostrategical reasons rather than economic reason.

2. Methodology

This paper uses a qualitative method, with the data collected using document and internet-based method (Bakry, 2019). Primary data used are documents and reports on US foreign aid to Israel from 2017 to 2020 published

directly by the US government through one of their research institutions. This primary data will be supplemented by secondary data from books, journals, previous research, news, and articles that discuss US foreign aid to Israel. To analyze and interpret the data that has been collected, the author uses the analysis technique by Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña (2014) which includes data reduction, data presentation, and data verification.

3. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

3.1 Foreign Aid

Broadly speaking, foreign aid is the international provision of capital, goods, or services from a country or international organization for the benefit of the recipient country or its people. Such assistance can be economic, military, or humanitarian. Foreign aid can involve the provision of financial resources or commodities (for example, food or military equipment) or even technical training. The Development Assistance Committee (DAC) of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) defines foreign aid as a flow of resources provided by official institutions on concessional financial terms with a view to promoting economic development (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2022). Resources can be economic in nature, such as financial contributions, but can also include technical assistance and commodities (such as food aid or agricultural equipment). The cost of humanitarian assistance in peacekeeping operations may also be considered foreign aid. Some countries include the gift or sale of military equipment as foreign aid.

When it comes to international politics, foreign aid is used primarily to promote geostrategic interests, for the right to build and maintain foreign bases, to strengthen alliances, or to keep allied regimes in power. Foreign aid is also used to maintain friendly relations with foreign governments. Foreign aid facilitates cooperation, and builds strong alliances for several reasons. First, foreign aid can be used to keep a country as an ally. By economically or militarily supporting a friendly foreign government, the giving state can prevent the receiving state from falling into the enemy's camp. Second, foreign aid can be given in an attempt to gain foreign allies. And third, foreign aid can be used to win the hearts and minds of the population (Apodaca, 2017).

While foreign aid has several purposes, not least of which is the desire to improve human welfare, the primary reason for the allocation of foreign aid is to pursue foreign policy objectives. The strategic and commercial interests of donor countries are the primary drivers behind many foreign aid programs. Foreign aid is therefore one of a number of tools that policymakers can use to advance their foreign policy objectives. Foreign aid also allows the giving country access and influence in the domestic and foreign affairs of other countries. Tarnoff and Lawson report that US leaders and policymakers view foreign aid as an important instrument of US foreign policy that is increasingly linked to national security policy (Tarnoff & Lawson, 2016).

3.2 Bilateral Relations

Bilateral relations are a basic element of international relations. The central role of bilateral relations in diplomacy can then be explored through its strategic role in promoting national interests and international negotiations. Through foreign ministries, embassies and consulates, bilateral diplomacy indeed remains the best tool to pursue a country's interests, whether through trade and investment, by promoting a country's image and culture, or by communicating with the diaspora. Moreover, bilateral relations are an important phase for engaging in international negotiations, as common interests are first developed at the bilateral level to build coalitions and more effectively highlight those interests in multilateral negotiations.

There are different types of relationships that occur in a bilateral relationship, from friendships and special relationships to hostilities and other conflictual relationships. Bilateral relationships may also be symmetrical or asymmetrical, involve dependencies or interdependencies, be institutionalized or not, consensual or not, new or old, and be based on shared interests and/or values. Pannier classifies a bilateral relationship into two types: privileged bilateral relations (cooperative relations) and conflictual Bilateral Relations (conflictual relations) (Pannier, 2020).

4. Results

4.1 United States Foreign Aid to Israel

United States foreign aid is assistance provided by the United States to other countries. Foreign aid is the largest component of the international budget and is viewed by many members of the United States Congress as an important instrument of United States foreign policy. For national security, commercial, and humanitarian reasons, U.S. foreign aid flows through many U.S. federal agencies and supports a variety of objectives. These objectives include promoting economic growth, reducing poverty, enhancing cooperation, expanding access to health care and education, establishing stability in conflict areas, countering terrorism, promoting human rights, strengthening allied countries, and curtailing the production and trafficking of illegal drugs. Most United States foreign aid is administered by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID), the Millennium Challenge Corporation (MCC), the United States Departments of State (DOS), the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), the United States Department of the Treasury (USDT), the United States Department of Defense (DOD), or through multilateral organizations (Morgenstern & Brown, 2022).

It has been mentioned earlier that most US foreign aid to Israel takes the form of military aid. This is mainly due to the United States' commitment to Israel's qualitative military edge (QME) that dates back to Lyndon Johnson's presidency. The United States considers Israel to be its most valuable liberal representative and ally in the Middle East, and, as such, Israel's presence in the region is a vital part of the United States' national interests. In order to ensure Israel's survival among countries that have long disliked its existence, Israel must be able to defend itself militarily and deter potential aggression. In this endeavor, Israel will always be quantitatively outnumbered in terms of artillery, tanks and planes that a coalition of Arab states can deploy. Israel's continued survival can be ensured only if it is able to maintain a qualitative military advantage, relying on superior weaponry, tactics, training, leadership and other factors of military effectiveness to confront and defeat its quantitatively superior adversaries in the Middle East.

In addition, there is the threat from Iran, which has become more visible recently. Iran poses a threat to the United States and Israel because of its sponsorship of terrorism, support for the insurgency in Iraq, and efforts to develop weapons of mass destruction. Iran's aggressive foreign policy and hegemonic aspirations, as demonstrated by its assistance to militants in Iraq, Lebanon, Afghanistan and the Palestinian territories, further attest to the threat to regional stability posed by Iran. Over the years, Iran has used terrorism as a means to project power and counter its enemies in the Middle East. The US State Department has even named Iran as the most active state for sponsoring terrorism, stating that the Ministry of Intelligence and Security and the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps (IRGC) provide Hezbollah terrorist groups in Lebanon and in Palestine especially Hamas, Palestinian Islamic Jihad (PIJ), al-Aqsa Martyrs Brigades, and the Popular Front for the Liberation of Palestine with funds, safe havens, training, and weapons (Wunderle & Briere, 2008).

Technological development is the next concern Israel has. Although Israel currently has a convincing qualitative military advantage over its adversaries, new technologies from drones, missiles and cyber will threaten that advantage. Israel's main adversaries have sought to mask their relative military weaknesses through new technologies. For example, Hamas has used small drones to attack Israel. Hezbollah is also trying to gain access to precision missiles that will pose new threats to Israel's security (Sachs & Huggard, 2020). Israel's adversaries will be able to increase their ability to threaten Israel due to the emergence of several new technological innovations. Automated or unmanned vehicles, whether on the ground or in the air, allow Israel's enemies to gain a tactical advantage in penetrating defense layers. Cyber warfare offers new alternatives for attacking targets, and allows attackers to more easily conceal their identity. For state and non-state actors alike, such attacks are particularly attractive given the low effort involved. If indeed cyber defenses prove to be resilient, follow-up cyberattacks can be carried out without much effort.

When associated with the concept of foreign aid proposed by Robinson and Tarp (2000), it can be seen in the case of US foreign aid to Israel that the main reason the United States wants to provide foreign aid is for reasons of foreign policy and national security. National security in this case includes not only the domestic United States

but also its allies. In recent years, several new threats to Israel's security have emerged. These threats come not only from state actors but also from non-state actors. The biggest threat mainly comes from state actors, namely Iran. As the United States' main ally in the Middle East, Israel must be able to maintain its existence in the region. The United States realizes that with the emergence of this new threat, Israel will not be able to maintain its existence without their help. Therefore, in an effort to help Israel in this regard, the United States provides foreign aid to Israel.

According to the author's analysis, the provision of foreign aid from the United States to Israel is also a manifestation of the close bilateral relations between the United States and Israel that have existed since the formation of the state of Israel. The author mentions that there is a relationship between the concept of foreign aid and the concept of bilateral relations that the author uses. In this case, foreign aid is an implication of a bilateral relationship. The bilateral relationship formed between the United States and Israel is a privileged bilateral relationship formed due to proximity and shared history. It is important for both countries to maintain the bilateral relationship because the relationship they have established is in the national interest of both countries. To realize this effort, the United States also provides foreign aid to Israel so that the bilateral relationship between the two countries can effectively face the threats mentioned.

The provision of foreign aid by the United States to Israel is also in line with the United States' long-standing commitment to Israel's qualitative military edge (QME). This commitment has been in place since the 1970s to ensure that Israel is able to defend itself militarily and deter potential aggression from its enemies (Wunderle & Briere, 2008). US foreign aid, especially in the form of military aid, plays a very important role in realizing Israel's QME. Through this military aid, Israel can obtain advanced and capable military equipment from the United States. The presence of these equipment in the Israeli military will certainly strengthen Israel's military superiority over its enemies, which as a result will become Israel's instrument for deterrence.

4.2 Forms of Foreign Aid

4.2.1 Military

Military aid is aid used to assist a country in its defense efforts, or to help a country maintain control of its territory. This aid can be given to a foreign country in the form of money to buy weapons and equipment from the donor country. In the case between the United States and Israel, the military aid Israel received in 2017-2020 included the F-35 Fighter, M1 Abrams APC, KC-46A Pegasus, Iron Dome, David's Sling, Arrow I, Arrow II, Arrow III, and United States emergency military supplies stationed in Israel (Sharp, 2020).

United States foreign aid to Israel is one of the United States' efforts to fulfill their commitment to Israel's qualitative military edge which will ultimately help Israel maintain its existence. The United States and Israel are aware that quantitatively, Israel will not be able to surpass the military power of its enemies, most of which are Israel's neighbors. Moreover, there is a new threat from Iran with its nuclear and ballistic missiles.

New military technologies, meanwhile, will threaten to influence and even make Israel's qualitative military advantage irrelevant. This will make non-state actors and weak states a serious threat over the next 10 to 20 years (Sachs & Huggard, 2020). The falling cost of unmanned systems and weapons, from easily coordinated drones to a plethora of precision missiles that can overwhelm Israel's missile defenses, will pose a new threat to Israel, no matter how advanced its military is. The development and proliferation of cyber technology and know-how will also likely continue to play a large role in future conflicts. Israel's existence is also inseparable from the threat of terrorism. This threat is also the cause of providing military assistance in US foreign aid to Israel. Countries tend to cooperate in the military field when they realize that they are under the threat of terrorism (Juned & Saripudin, 2017).

According to the author's analysis, it is very important for the United States to continue to ensure that Israel retains a qualitative military advantage over its enemies. One of the things that the United States can and has done is to

help Israel militarily through their foreign aid. The United States' military assistance began with the transfer of military equipment such as the F-35 Fighter, M1 Abrams APC, KC-46A Tanker to US support for Israel's rocket and missile defenses. All of this military assistance is also in accordance with Israel's defense doctrine which is based on four main pillars: deterrence, early warning, active defense and rapid and decisive response on the battlefield (Sönmez & Batu, 2021).

4.2.2 Non-military

In addition to the military aid, US foreign aid to Israel for 2017-2020 also includes non-military aid consisting of Migration & Refugee Assistance, Loan Guarantees, American Schools and Hospitals Abroad Program (ASHA), and cooperation between the two countries in the scientific and business fields.

In Sachs and Huggard's opinion, there are several other factors that will make deep instability likely to continue in the Middle East in the next two decades. Climate change will probably be the most dangerous. The Middle East will in future experience more frequent droughts. Reduced flows in important rivers such as those in Syria and Iraq, rising sea levels that will threaten to flood low-lying areas of the Persian Gulf, rising summer temperatures that could make large parts of the Middle East uninhabitable. Combined, these extreme conditions among several countries in the region, including for some of the poorest and most densely populated countries, will increase the likelihood of economic crises, regime instability, and result in new large migration and refugee flows both in the directly affected countries and beyond, which could certainly pose a threat to Israel's security (Sachs & Huggard, 2020).

Because of these threats, the author mentions that the United States and Israel cannot just focus foreign aid from the United States on the military field alone. Although the amount is still relatively small, both countries seem to have realized the dangers of these threats and have begun to address them in US foreign aid to Israel. This can be seen in the non-military aid that the United States has provided to Israel, which deals with areas such as migration, economics, health, agricultural science, energy, and water. In modern times, the things that can threaten a country's security are no longer just traditional fields, but also non-traditional fields as mentioned earlier. Therefore, the United States' foreign aid to Israel in the non-military field is expected to help Israel maintain national security and maintain their survival in the Middle East as the United States' main ally in the region.

4.3 Process of US Foreign Aid to Israel

Based on the explanation above, it can be seen that most of the United States' foreign aid to Israel in 2017-2020 was military aid. The provision of military assistance must go through a fairly complex process first, especially for material military assistance. As previously explained, the United States provides this military assistance through a program called Foreign Military Financing (FMF). The FMF program provides grants and loans to help Israel buy weapons and defense equipment manufactured in the United States.

The process of acquiring this military equipment is a bit complex. First, the President of the United States must authorize the transfer of US defense equipment and services to Israel. Then, under the Foreign Military Sales (FMS) program, the US Department of Defense will acquire goods or services from US contractors on behalf of Israel. Next, through FMF, the US Department of Defense provides grants to Israel to purchase the US military equipment.

The Foreign Military Sales (FMS) program is part of the security assistance authorized by the Arms Export Control Act (AECA) and is a basic tool of US foreign policy. Under Section 3 of the AECA, the United States can sell defense equipment and services to foreign countries and international organizations when the President of the United States makes a determination that the prospective buyer is eligible. The FMS program is conducted through binding contractual agreements between the United States government and foreign buyers. These intergovernmental agreements to transfer defense equipment and services are called Letters of Offer and

Acceptance (LOA). The FMS process is complex and, in the case of defense equipment sales, can last for years. The stages of the FMS process are outlined in Table 1

Table 1: Foreign Military Sales (FMS) Process

Pre-Case Development	Preliminary Indefinite Time Period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer identifies defense capabilities gaps • Customer researches options/sources • Customer refines requirements • Customer and U.S. exchange technical information
	Request Indefinite Time Period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer prepares Letter of Request (LOR) in the forms of price and availability (P&A) and/or Letter of Offer and Acceptance (LOA) • Country Team Assessment (CTA) • LOR Channels of Submission • Security Assistance survey teams
Case Development	Offer 45-150 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DSCA receives and evaluate LOR DSCA Case Writing Division (CWD) finalizes LOA • DSCA-CWD countersigns LOA after DSCA HQ & Department of State (DoS) approval • DSCA issues LOA to customer
	Acceptance 85 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer signs LOA by Offer Expiration Date • Customer sends signed LOA and Initial Deposit to Defense Finance and Accounting Service – Security Cooperation Accounting (DFAS-SCA)
Case Implementation and Execution	Implementation 10-15 days average	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DFAS issues Obligational Authority (OA) • DSCA issues implementing directive
	Execution Longest phase: depends on delivery schedule	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Articles/services/training are ordered/contracted • Articles shipped and services performed • DSCA reports performance and deliveries to customer / DFAS-SCA
	Closure 2 years from completion of execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IA / DFAS / customer reconcile records • DSCA sends closure certificate to DFAS-SCA • DFAS-SCA issues final bill to customer

Source 1: (Defense Security Cooperation Agency, 2021)

After looking at the stages of the process that a country must go through to make a purchase through the FMS program, the author argues that these stages are too complicated. In the case of Israel, for example, the process of

purchasing the F-35 Fighter took six years (Sharp, 2016). Another example is the purchase of the KC-46A Tanker Aircraft, which can only be delivered to Israel in 2024 at the earliest (Cicurel, 2022).

While Israel had to go through the lengthy sales process, Iran, which since 2017 has become the biggest threat to the United States and Israel in the Middle East, has further strengthened its military capabilities with nuclear weapons and ballistic missiles. Iran's military area of operations has also grown significantly since 2016, when it began arming Hezbollah in Lebanon, which has since become a major threat to Israel. Iran is also building proxy forces in Syria, Iraq and Yemen, and developing increasingly precise missiles and other advanced weapons for them and Hezbollah (Stavridis, Wald, Gardner, & Obering, 2019).

Iran's hegemonic ambitions in the Middle East have also resulted in a broader arms race among Iran, Arab states and Turkey that further jeopardizes Israel's qualitative military edge. Despite the constraints imposed by economic sanctions, Iran's defense budget is more or less on par with Israel's. Iran has also spent years developing their sizable domestic arms industry, including to arm their proxies such as Hezbollah. While the quality of Iran's weapons production arguably lags behind that of Israel's, Iran is the largest producer of ballistic missiles in the Middle East while continuously improving the range, payload and accuracy of its ballistic missiles.

According to the author's analysis, these developments would raise the very real possibility of a major war between Israel and Iran that could spill over into much of the Middle East. If such a conflict were to occur, the entire territory of Israel would become the front line. Such a conflict would also result in unprecedented operational demands on Israel, including intense fighting on multiple fronts simultaneously. If Israel has to go through this lengthy process that could last for years every time it purchases military equipment through the FMS program, Israel's qualitative military advantage will be threatened. Strengthening Israel's military capabilities is critical and urgent to the national security of the United States. A strong and self-defense capable Israel is in the interest of the United States. With its own regional presence and uncertain future commitments, the United States is increasingly dependent on Israel to uphold Middle East stability and stop the growing aggression of their common enemies such as Iran.

Most Israeli purchases are made through the US government, which buys defense goods from US companies and sells them to Israel at a higher price. The alternative is direct commercial sales (DCS), where Israel buys equipment directly from US companies. DCS is considered a more flexible process, as the customer country can consult directly with the companies about the specific products and services it needs. The customer country can utilize more negotiating power regarding the type of contract, how the contract is defined, final delivery terms, and payment methods. United States companies do prefer DCS because it is more favorable to them and thus tends to speed up the delivery of goods to that customer country. However, generally foreign buyers, in this case Israel, have to go through an arduous process first to obtain a DCS license from the United States government. Therefore, Israel can make it a top priority to undertake and complete the DCS licensing process so that they can make direct purchases from Boeing (for KC-46A), Raytheon (for Iron Dome and David's Sling), and Lockheed Martin (for F-35) (Stavridis, Wald, Gardner, & Obering, 2019).

5. Conclusion

Foreign aid is the largest component of the international budget and many members of the US Congress view foreign aid as an important tool of US foreign policy. When the author explains the concept of foreign aid, he mentions that one of the reasons countries provide foreign aid is for foreign policy purposes. This reason is especially true in the case of US foreign aid to Israel. As the author has explained, Israel is not a poor or economically weak country, but rather Israel can be classified as a developed country with a very good economy. Therefore, it can be concluded that the provision of foreign aid by the United States is not for humanitarian purposes, altruism, or economic development, but to fulfill the foreign policy objectives of the United States.

In terms of numbers, Israel has been the largest recipient of US foreign aid since World War II. This is due to the United States' strong support for Israel and its security, the two countries' shared strategic goals in the Middle East, a shared commitment to democratic values, and the United States' support for Israel's independence. To date, the

United States has provided Israel with approximately \$146 billion in bilateral aid and missile defense funding. Currently, especially in 2017-2020, almost all of the United States' foreign aid to Israel comes in the form of military aid, although Israel has also received significant economic aid.

The provision of military assistance as part of the United States' foreign aid to Israel must first go through a fairly complex process, especially for material military assistance carried out through the Foreign Military Sales (FMS) Program. The United States can sell defense equipment and services to foreign countries and international organizations when the President of the United States makes a determination that the prospective buyer is eligible. The FMS program is implemented through binding contractual agreements between the United States government and foreign buyers. The FMS process is complex and, in the case of defense equipment sales, can last for years. In practice, the FMS sales process goes through three stages: pre-case development, case development, and finally case implementation and execution.

The author concludes that the form of US foreign aid to Israel consists of two fields, namely military and non-military. For the military field, Israel receives foreign aid from the United States in the form of the F-35 Fighter, Namer APC, KC-46A Pegasus, Iron Dome, David's Sling, Arrow I, Arrow II, Arrow III, and United States emergency military supplies stationed in Israel. In addition to the military field, Israel also receives foreign aid for non-military fields in the form of Migration & Refugee Assistance, Loan Guarantees, American Schools and Hospitals Abroad Program (ASHA), as well as cooperation between the two countries in the scientific and business fields. Regarding the process, the author mentions that the process of providing foreign aid in 2017-2020 has been going relatively well, although for the FMS program, there are a few obstacles due to the long duration of the FMS process. Nevertheless, the author still concludes that the form and process of US foreign aid to Israel in 2017-2020 are in line with the US commitment to Israel's survival. As a result, the provision of US foreign aid to Israel shows Israel's interdependence on the United States militarily and non-militarily. In addition, the continuous provision of foreign aid also shows the strengthening of bilateral relations between the United States and Israel. However, this interdependence can potentially be a negative thing for Israel if they cannot evolve their military equipment because they only expect foreign aid from the United States. Therefore, in this case, Israel must also be able to act independently.

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